

Deliverable 9.5: Final assessment of TNA provided to ATMO-ACCESS facilities

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1 Introduction

This document delivers the final assessment of the TransNational Access (TNA) provided during the ATMO-ACCESS project (Solutions for Sustainable Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities). Previous Deliverables D9.1 “First assessment of TNA provided to ATMO-ACCESS facilities”, D9.2 “Second assessment of TNA provided to ATMO-ACCESS facilities”, and D9.3 “Third assessment of TNA provided to ATMO-ACCESS facilities” contain extensive information on the TNA activities carried out during successive one-year periods since the project's start. This report covers the overall physical, remote and hybrid access provision to users by the 61 European atmospheric research facilities of the ACTRIS, ICOS, and IAGOS RIs throughout the entire project duration, from October 2021 to April 2025.

2 Summary of overall Transnational Access activity to Facilities

ATMO-ACCESS supported access provision to 61 facilities belonging to the participating Research Infrastructures, as listed in Table 1.

Table 1 - List of Facilities providing TA

#	Facility type	Facility name	Acronym
1	Observational	Andalusian Global ObseRvatory of the Atmosphere	AGORA, ES
2	Observational	Atmospheric Sounding Station El Arenosillo	ARN, ES
3	Observational	AThens MOonitoring Supersite	ATMOS, GR
4	Observational	Barcelona Cluster	BCN, ES
5	Observational	Cyprus Atmospheric Observatory	CAO, CY
6	Observational	Cabauw Experimental Site for Atmospheric Research	CESAR, NL
7	Observational	CNR-IMAA Atmospheric Observatory	CIAO, IT
8	Observational	Monte Cimone - Po Valley	CMN-PV, IT
9	Observational	Cape Verde Atmospheric Observatory	CVAO, CV
10	Observational	Cézeaux-Aulnat Opme Puy de Dôme	CO-PDD, FR
11	Observational	EVora Atmospheric Science Observatory	EVASO, PT
12	Observational	Finokalia	FKL, GR
13	Observational	Pallas-Sodankylä Atmosphere-Ecosystem Supersite	FMI PAL-SOD, FI

14	Observational	Mace Head Atmospheric Research Station	MHD, IE
15	Observational	Hyltemossa Research Station	HTM, SE
16	Observational	ISAF - Izaña Observatory (IZO)	ISAF - (IZO), ES
17	Observational	High Altitude Research Station Jungfrauoch	JFJ, CH
18	Observational	TROPOS Research Station Melpitz	Melpitz, DE
19	Observational	National Atmospheric Observatory Košetice	NAOK, CZ
20	Observational	Observatoire de Physique de l'Atmosphère à La Réunion	OPAR, FR
21	Observational	PANhellenic GEophysical observatory of Antikythera	PANGEA, GR
22	Observational	Romanian Atmospheric 3D research Observatory	RADO, RO
23	Observational	Sonnblick Observatory	SBO, AT
24	Observational	Site Instrumental de Recherche par Télédétection Atmosphérique	SIRTA, FR
25	Observational	Station for Measuring Ecosystem - Atmosphere Relations II	SMEAR II, FI
26	Observational	Station for Measuring Ecosystem - Atmosphere Relations Estonia	SMEAR Estonia, EE
27	Observational	Villum Research Station	VRS, GL
28	Observational	Wrocław Observatory Platform for Atmospheric Studies	WOPAS, PL
29	Observational	Warsaw Observatory Station	WOS, PL
30	Sim. Chamber	Aerosol Chamber of the Atmospheric Chemistry Department (ACD-C) and Turbulent Leipzig Aerosol Cloud Interaction Simulator (LACIS-T)	ACD-C / LACIS-T, DE
31	Sim. Chamber	Aerosol Interaction and Dynamics in the Atmosphere	AIDA, DE
32	Sim. Chamber	Aarhus University Research on Aerosols chamber	AURA, DK
33	Sim. Chamber	Experimental Multiphase Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	CESAM, FR

34	Sim. Chamber	Chamber for Atmospheric Modelling and Bio-Aerosol Research	ChAMBRe, IT
35	Sim. Chamber	Environmental Simulation Chamber from the "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University	ESC-Q-UAIC, RO
36	Sim. Chamber	European PHOto reactor	EUPHORE, ES
37	Sim. Chamber	Outdoor Atmospheric Simulation Chamber of Orléans	HELIOS, FR
38	Sim. Chamber	Irish Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	IASC, IE
39	Sim. Chamber	Kuopio atmospheric simulation chambers	KASCs, FI
40	Sim. Chamber	Manchester Aerosol Chamber	MAC, UK
41	Sim. Chamber	PSI Atmospheric Chemistry Simulation Chambers	PACS-C2, CH
42	Sim. Chamber	Quartz Reactor	QUAREC, DE
43	Sim. Chamber	Simulation of Atmospheric Photochemistry in a Large Reaction Chamber	SAPHIR, DE
44	Mobile	FORTH Mobile Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	FORTH-MSC, GR
45	Mobile	ACTRIS-Poland Mobile Platform	AMP, PL
46	Mobile	Finland Combined Mobile Laboratory	FCoMLab, FI
47	Mobile	The ICOS mobile laboratory	ICOS-ATC, FR
48	Mobile	Leipzig Aerosol and Cloud Remote Observations System	LACROS, DE
49	Mobile	Unmanned Systems Research Laboratory	USRL, CY
50	Central Lab	Centre for Reactive Trace Gases In Situ Measurements	CI GAS-CH, CH
51	Central Lab	Integrated Carbon Observation System Atmospheric Thematic Center	ICOS-ATC, FR (CL)
52	Central Lab	Prague Aerosol Calibration Centre	PACC, CZ
53	Central Lab	World Calibration Center for Aerosol Physics	WCCAP, DE
54	Central Lab	Aerosol Chemical Monitor Calibration Centre	ACMCC @SIRTA, FR
55	Central Lab	ACTRIS Centre for Cloud Remote Sensing – France	CCRES-FR @SIRTA, FR

56	Central Lab	ACTRIS Centre for Cloud Remote Sensing – NL	CCRES-NL @CESAR, NL
57	Central Lab	Isotope laboratory at Utrecht University	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL
58	Central Lab	CNR Lidar calibration centre	CARS-CNR @CIAO, IT
59	Central Lab	ACTRIS Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing at Izaña Subtropical Facility	CARS-ES @ISAF, ES
60	Central Lab	Lidar Calibration Centre	CARS-RO @RADO, RO
61	Central Lab	Centre for Cloud Ice Nucleation	CCIce @AIDA, DE

Figure 1 provides the geographical distribution of the facilities offering TNA in the project. Most TNA activities involved ACTRIS and, to a lesser extent, ICOS, which mainly offers virtual access to data. IAGOS was not engaged in any TNA because physical, remote or hybrid access isn't possible due to the unique nature of the RI. Nevertheless, the ACTRIS-ICOS co-located facilities had a valuable opportunity to test providing physical, remote, and virtual access. Most importantly, these facilities were able to experiment with and become familiar with harmonised access procedures.

Figure 1 - Map of Facilities providing TNA within ATMO-ACCESS

Transnational access provision was organised and managed following the sequence of calls designed in the TNA programme released in Work Package 7. A total of 13 TNA Calls were prepared, managed and monitored in Work Package 9, including 7 regular calls for TNA and 6 special calls, as follows:

A. Regular Calls:

- 1st TNA Call – General, based on existing best practices and expertise across the RIs.
- 2nd TNA Call – Topical (Green Deal Call)
- 3rd TNA Call – General
- 4th TNA Call – Topical (Remote and Hybrid access)
- 5th TNA Call – General
- 6th TNA Call – Topical (Multidisciplinary access)
- 7th TNA Call – General

B. Special Calls:

- 1st annual Call for Pilot Private Sector TNA (2023).
- 2nd annual Call for Pilot Private Sector TNA (2024).
- 1st Call for Pilot Training TNA – AGORA Aerosol Training Course: Characterisation of atmospheric aerosol using in-situ and remote sensing techniques (2023), in collaboration with WP4 “Developing and optimally integrating joint training services”.
- 2nd Call for Pilot Training TNA – Sensors and Drones in Atmospheric Science (Autumn School in Switzerland and Cyprus, 2024), in collaboration with WP4.
- Call for Pilot TNA to support the Cal/Val of satellite atmospheric missions, prepared and implemented in close collaboration with WP6 “New trans-national access modalities to support research, technology and innovation”.
- Call for Pilot Fast-Track TNA.

A total of 418 applications were collected under these calls, processed following the access process described in D9.1, and evaluated according to the guidelines and criteria detailed in the TNA general evaluation guidelines, which were produced and regularly updated by the WP9 team. A comprehensive analysis of the TNA proposals evaluation and selection, including scores and success rates, can be found in WP7 deliverables.

313 TNAs successfully passed the selection and were accepted, with an overall success rate of 75%. The WP9 team also took care of monitoring the implementation of the approved TNA projects, supporting the users and the providers in the process, and finally reporting all the activities. 296 TNA projects were completed, and only 17 were cancelled due to unexpected circumstances affecting the user or the provider.

Figure 2 provides a comprehensive overview of the transnational access activity, illustrating the calls’ results, the number of proposals received and accepted, as well as the TNA completed and those cancelled. Complete details and insights on the TA projects implemented at the

facilities, as well as on the ATMO-ACCESS users, are provided in Sections 2.1 and 2.2, respectively.

Figure 2 - ATMO-ACCESS Total TNA Projects: Applications Received vs. Approved, Cancelled and Completed

2.1 Data and insights from completed TNA projects

Analysis of data from the completed TNA projects shows that exactly 50% of the successful TNAs involved physical access, with hybrid access (a combination of physical and remote access) accounting for 38%, and remote access only making up the remaining 12%. This data is particularly relevant when considering the impact of COVID-19 on researchers' mobility due to imposed restrictions or self-restraint during the first 18 months of the project. Overall, the data suggests that while hybrid and remote modalities are increasingly used, especially for research and technical services, physical access is still largely preferred. Figure 3 shows how the different

access types were used across the different types of services. Physical access remains the main modality for use of the training services (80%), underscoring the importance of in-person interaction for effective learning and skill development. It is also widely used for technical services (47%), and accounts for 44% of the use of research/innovation services. Hybrid access is widely used for research/innovation services (46%), reflecting the growing trend of combining on-site and remote methods to support complex scientific work. It is less frequently chosen for technical services (25%) and even less, as seen, for training services (13%). Overall, remote access is used less than other types, and more for technical services (28%) than for research/innovation (10%) and training (7%). This suggests that certain technical support functions can be effectively delivered remotely, while training and research activities still benefit more from physical presence at the facility.

Figure 3 - Distribution of access types across the types of services provided

RIs' facilities providing transnational access in ATMO-ACCESS were:

- 29 Observational Facilities (OBS), ground-based stations for long-term observations of atmospheric constituents that deliver long-term data based on a regular measurement schedule and common operation standards.
- 14 Simulation Chamber Facilities (ASC), used to perform dedicated experiments under controlled conditions.
- 6 Mobile Facilities (MOB).
- 12 Central Laboratories (CL), of which 4 are singular CL and 8 are co-located with OF (7), and MF (1).

Observational facilities were the most frequently used (55%), followed by simulation chambers (25%), central laboratories (13%), and finally mobile facilities (7%). It's also interesting to note that 22 TA projects implemented access to multiple facilities, taking advantage of this valuable opportunity offered to users for the first time.

Figure 4 and Figure 5 offer, respectively, a breakdown of the total TNA projects carried out at different types of facilities, by type of service, and by type of access requested.

Figure 4 – TNA projects by facility and type of service accessed

Figure 5 – TNA projects by facility and type of access

2.2 ATMO-ACCESS User metrics

A total of 1231 users requested access to ATMO-ACCESS facilities, 992 were involved in the approved TNA projects, and ultimately 780 actually accessed the requested facilities.

Figure 6 - ATMO-ACCESS users requesting access, approved for access, and actually accessing the facilities and services

Graphs in this section illustrate the characteristics of users in the approved TNA projects carried out at the facilities, including their role in the user group, nationality, affiliation, profile, and field of research activity. Gender participation in the TNA activities is detailed in section 3.

The majority of users: never accessed the facilities before (Figure 7), work in countries where similar facilities do not exist (Figure 8), and come from universities and higher education institutions (Figure 9) that are not beneficiaries in ATMO-ACCESS (Figure 10).

Figure 7 - New Users

Figure 8 - Presence of similar facilities in users' countries of employment

Figure 9 - User institutions' legal status

Figure 10 – ATMO-ACCESS Internal/External Users

Regarding the profiles, users requesting access to the ATMO-ACCESS facilities are mostly experienced scientists, often accompanied by postgraduate students from their research groups (Figure 11). The research field is almost always the atmosphere, followed at a considerable distance by engineering and technology, chemistry, and the eco-biosphere (Figure 12).

Figure 11 – ATMO-ACCESS User profiles

Figure 12 – ATMO-ACCESS User fields of activity

Finally, regarding the geographical distribution of users, Figure 13 and Figure 14 show the users' country of origin (affiliation) and country of nationality, respectively. Germany, France, and Italy are the main EU countries from which users originate and, with slight differences in order, also the ones with the highest number of nationals among users.

Figure 13 – ATMO-ACCESS User affiliation countries

Figure 14 - ATMO-ACCESS User country of nationality

Figure 15 provides more details on the 249 users originating from non-EU countries, primarily from the United States (20%) and Latin American countries (8% from Argentina, Brazil, and Colombia), followed by Asia and Oceania (18%), and finally Africa (2%). However, non-EU European countries account for more than half of the international users (52%).

Figure 15 - ATMO-ACCESS International user country of origin

3 Focus on modalities of gender participation in TNA projects

Since the start of the TNA activities, the WP9 team has worked to support gender-diverse user teams and anticipate and resolve potential gender inequalities at every stage of the TNA cycle, in accordance with the Grant Agreement's criteria to strive for gender equality. Specifically, in the day-to-day administration of the access process, the TNA Team/SAMU made sure to take all necessary steps to ensure equitable opportunities in the application of TNAs, addressing any possible problems in all the phases of the TNA process. Examples of these efforts are the extended deadlines for submitting proposals, granted upon request to various applicants in the 1st, 4th and 6th calls due to personal conditions or social responsibilities (children, domestic care, elderly care, etc.); the additional time for completing the reviews, in the evaluation phase, granted to experts in the Access Evaluation Panel on the same grounds; and the recommendation to providers to offer remote access, enabling users to carry out their activities despite specific challenges (e.g., pregnancy, COVID-related issues, or other disabilities).

The results of this effort are encouraging, although the way to achieve gender equality is still long and demands actions at different, higher levels (welfare solutions, policies, support) to really make a difference.

Figure 16 below shows the gender representation in the ATMO-ACCESS TNAs awarded so far in the project, providing the percentages of male and female scientists who have managed to obtain TNA funding and those who haven't. It is useful to remind here that in all the calls considered, males were always by far the majority of applicants.

Figure 16 - Gender divide in TNA success rate, per TNA Call

Overall, female participation accounts for 36% of total users, both as user group members (36%) and lead applicants (35%), as shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17 – ATMO-ACCESS User gender distribution and role in the group

The next graph presents an overview of actual modalities of gender participation in the TNA activities based on the type of access used to access the facilities.

As Figure 18 below illustrates, there are no major differences in the types of access (physical, remote, hybrid) actually utilised by men or women.

Figure 18 - Type of access utilised by Gender

4 Total quantity of access provided

The total number of access units provided to users via physical, remote and hybrid access reached 9,184.65 units, representing more than 111% of the total access planned in ATMO-ACCESS. Providers chose to complete the approved user projects and continue offering access, even by supplementing the necessary resources with other funding sources (e.g., institutional funds), in cases where additional project funding may be unavailable following budget adjustments at the end of the project.

Table 2 presents the complete list of facilities involved in TNA provision in ATMO-ACCESS with information on the units of access applied, the minimum quantity of access estimated for the entire project, and details of the access units provided, including the fast-track access, the private sector call, the call for the pilot AGORA TNA training and the pilot Cal/Val TNA for international stakeholders.

Table 2: Quantity of access provided

Infrastr. Short Name	Unit of Access ¹	Min. Quant. Of Access (A)	1st call	2nd call	3rd call	4th call	5th call	6th call	7th call	Private sector TNA call	Fast-Track TNA	Pilot Training 1-2	Pilot Cal/Val	Total Access Provided (B)	Difference (B-A)	PROVIDED %
CESAM	DAY	81	22	5	15	34	25							101	20	124.69%
HELIOS	DAY	54	33			21			10					64	10	118.52%
OPAR	DAY	160	84					14	26				59	183	23	114.38%
SIRTA-CCRES-ACMCC	UWD	150		4.5									44	48.5	-101.5	32.33%
SIRTA-Obs	UWD	277	18	89	107				44	69			86	413	136	149.10%
CO-PDD	UWD	250					25			39			54	118	-132	47.20%
ICOS ATC	SWD	234												0	-234	0.00%
KASC	DAY	50	40		21									61	11	122.00%
FCoMLab	DAY	28												0	-28	0.00%
PACS-C2	DAY	71	30	25	15		50	15						135	64	190.14%
JFJ	UWD	250		72	16		58							146	-104	58.40%
CIGAS-CH	SWD	124	60		72							30		162	38	130.65%
CESAR	UWD	151		39	23		261		50	4			11	388	237	256.95%
CESAR	SWD	750	382	67.5		250	48		90					837.5	87.5	111.67%
HTM	SWD	60					30		3					33	-27	55.00%
PANGEA	UWD	100					10						84	94	-6	94.00%
FKL	UWD	210	108		44		8		26					186	-24	88.57%
ATMOS	UWD	214	48	14	230		50		58	116				516	302	241.12%

¹ DAY is instrument/facility-day, UWD is user working day, SWD is staff working day.

FORTH-MSC	DAY	80	55					25					80	0	100.00%	
RADO	SWD	283	34					37	53			212	336	53	118.73%	
ESC-Q-UAIC	DAY	80		10	20	10		10	10				60	-20	75.00%	
IASC	DAY	100	20		5			25	15	30			95	-5	95.00%	
MAC	DAY	120	20		30			25		30			105	-15	87.50%	
EUPHORE	DAY	64	15	20	11		46						92	28	143.75%	
ISAF	SWD	40								1	5		6	-34	15.00%	
ISAF	SWD	116	30	9	59					1	18		117	1	100.86%	
AGORA	SWD	205	95.5				40		41			60	86	322.5	117.5	157.32%
BCN	UWD	110		50		70							120	10	109.09%	
BCN	UWD	90		13								85	98	8	108.89%	
CAO	DAY	120	11		20			21				25	70.5	147.5	27.5	122.92%
USRL	DAY	140	56	21	7			14	10			40.3	148.3	8.3	105.93%	
WOS	SWD	610	61.375				159.8	32.6	231.7			221	706.4	96.4	115.80%	
WOPAS	SWD	180						73	59.25				132.25	-47.75	73.47%	
AMP	SWD	100					36	33	34				103	3	103.00%	
CIAO	SWD	138			21		21					114	156	18	113.04%	
CMN-PV	UWD	220	142				28		97.7			10	277.7	57.7	126.23%	
ChAMBRe	DAY	120	41		12	18	22	10	21				124	4	103.33%	
VRS	UWD	64											0	-64	0.00%	
AURA	DAY	50	17			28							45	-5	90.00%	
NAOK	UWD	130					24						24	-106	18.46%	
PACC	SWD	108											0	-108	0.00%	
SBO	SWD	82	18	68		56		21	65				228	146	278.05%	
EVASO	UWD	70	14			7	14					49	84	14	120.00%	
SMEAR EE	SWD	153											0	-153	0.00%	
ARN	SWD	64					11.5		21.5			25	58	-6	90.63%	

CVAO	SWD	51											41	41	-10	80.39%
MEL	UWD	112												0	-112	0.00%
ACD-C / LACIS-T	DAY	82		20	10			30						60	-22	73.17%
WCCAP	SWD	65	4		8					20				32	-33	49.23%
LACROS	SWD	60	43										92	135	75	225.00%
MHD	DAY	60					20							20	-40	33.33%
SAPHIR / SAPHIR-PLUS	DAY	40	16	6		18	52							92	52	230.00%
AIDA	DAY	48	26		56		15	21						118	70	245.83%
QUAREC-ASC	DAY	122		10	50	15		51						126	4	103.28%
FMI PAL-SOD	UWD	250	139	65		16	87	228	4				46	585	335	234.00%
FCoMLab	DAY	60					18						85	103	43	171.67%
FCoMLab	DAY	50												0	-50	0.00%
SMEAR II	UWD	380	22		42	244	12	318					83	721	341	189.74%
		8231	1704.9	608	894	787	975.5	315.8	1461.8	701.9	23	115	1597.8	9184.65	923.65	111.22%

Access provision was fully driven by user demand, and consequently there are facilities that delivered substantially more/less access units than initially estimated. Facilities that provided far more units than foreseen effectively compensated for those that did receive fewer user requests. The TA budget was redistributed accordingly. The costs associated with the excess units were absorbed through provider contributions (especially in the case of long-lasting measurements campaigns, like for FMI PAL-SOD, or for the Cal/Val pilot) and/or project economies.

Seven facilities ultimately did not provide access for different reasons:

- ICOS ATC' service was still in the development pipeline, and unforeseen equipment constraints ultimately rendered it unavailable during the calls' periods.
- Despite promotional efforts, the services of some new facilities included in the project after its start (VRS, SMEAR EE) were less visible to the user community. The availability window did not align well with the user call schedule or with users' project timelines.
- Some users who initially requested access shifted their plans or no longer required the service.
- For some services the availability window did not align well with users' project timelines.

The full list of TNA projects completed at the facilities during the entire duration of ATMO-ACCESS is reported in Annex 1, with details on the user institution, title of the project, involved facility and completion.

5 Reference documents

- REF 1. ATMO-ACCESS Grant Agreement (ID: 101008004)
- REF 2. ATMO-ACCESS Deliverable 9.1: [First assessment of TNA provided to ATMO-ACCESS facilities](#), available on request.
- REF 3. ATMO-ACCESS Deliverable 9.2: [Second assessment of TNA provided to ATMO-ACCESS facilities, available on request.](#)
- REF 4. ATMO-ACCESS Deliverable 9.3: [Third assessment of TNA provided to ATMO-ACCESS facilities, available on request.](#)
- REF 5. [ATMO-ACCESS Milestone 9.4: Review of application, review and selection process for TNA to ATMO-ACCESS facilities](#)
- REF 6. AEP database of experts, available on request to WP9 Leader
- REF 7. [ATMO-ACCESS Terms Of Reference for the Access Evaluation Panel – AEP](#)
- REF 8. [ATMO-ACCESS General TNA Evaluation Guidelines](#)
- REF 9. ATMO-ACCESS Deliverable 6.3: [Proposed TNA pilots for innovators in technology](#)
- REF 10. European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *European charter for access to research infrastructures – Principles and guidelines for access and related services*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2015, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/524573>.

Annex 1 - List of TNA projects completed during ATMO-ACCESS

#	TNA Code	User Institution	Title & Acronym of the project	Host Facility/ies	STATUS
1	C1-FMI-PAL-SOD-1	schnaiTEC GmbH	Source apportionment of Arctic carbonaceous aerosol using the Angström exponent (SUPPOSE)	FMI PAL-SOD, FI (OBS)	Complete
2	C1-CHAMBRE-1	ETH Zürich, Switzerland	Survival of Antimicrobial Resistant Strains in the Air	ChAMBRé, IT (ASC)	Complete
3	C1-FORTH-MSC-2	Institute of Physical Chemistry PAS	The importance of sesquiterpene oxidation products for secondary organic aerosol formation – chamber experiments and field studies (SESQSOA)	FORTH-MSC, GR (MOB)	Complete
4	C1-AURA-1	University of Helsinki	Aarhus Chamber Campaign on Evaporation, Partitioning, and Terpene Oxidation (ACCEPTO)	AURA, DK (ASC)	Complete
5	C1-ISOLAB/CESAR-4	Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia	Methane Clumped isotopes in geological gas (MeClu)	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
6	C1-ISOLAB/CESAR-3	National University of Ireland Galway	MethAne ISoTope Measurements at Mace Head (MASTHAED)	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
7	C1-ISAF-IZO/Obs-1	University of Helsinki	Chasing preindustrial aerosols at Izaña	ISAF - IZO, ES (OBS)	Complete
8	C1-ISOLAB/CESAR-5	Stockholm University	Isotopic characterization of greenhouse gases – CO CH ₄ and CO ₂ - in sub-Saharan Africa background and urban environment.	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
9	C1-LACROS-1	Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich (ETH Zurich)	Dual operation of 35 and 94 GHz radar during a seeding experiment (DORSE)	LACROS, DE (MOB)	Complete

10	C1-SAPHIR-1	University of Lille	Comparison of instruments detecting atmospheric organic peroxy radicals (ROxCOMP)	SAPHIR, DE (ASC)	Complete
11	C1-ISOLAB/CESAR-6	Empa	R2D2	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
12	C1-AIDA-1	CNRS	AquaVIT-4 : International hygrometer intercomparison campaign	AIDA, DE (ASC)	Complete
13	C1- CMN-PV -1	University of Helsinki	New particle formation and its influence on air pollution in Po Valley	CMN-PV, IT (OBS)	Complete
14	C1-AGORA-1	Institute of Meteorology and Climate Research Atmospheric Aerosol Research (IMK-AAF)	Modular Observation Solution for Earth System (MOSE)	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
15	C1-PACS-C2-1	CNRS-IRCELYON	Novel Molecular Understanding of Aerosol Formation (NUCLEATE)	PACS-C2, CH (ASC)	Complete
16	C1-FKL-2	University of Strathclyde	Atmospheric Microplastics in the Mediterranean Sea Air (AtmoMedMP)	FKL, GR (OBS)	Complete
17	C1-CHAMBRE-2	University of Manchester	Validation of Real-time machine learning classification algorithms for the Detection of Airborne Pathogens using Novel Multi-Dimensional UV-LIF Spectrometers using Controlled ChamBRE Characterisation Experiments	ChAMBRé, IT (ASC)	Complete
18	C1-ISOLAB/CESAR-9	University of Wrocław	Characterization of GHG fluxes originating from landfill site based on carbon stable isotope analysis - (GHG landfill)	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete

19	C1-CiGAS-CH-1	University of Illinois at Urbana Champaign	Calibration and validation of a CRDS analyzer for isotopic fingerprinting of nitrous oxide emissions from an intensively agricultural region	CiGAS-CH, CH (CL)	Complete
20	C1-WCCAP-1	Aerosol d.o.o.	Intercomparison of optical absorption measurements using newly developed portable Aethalometer AE43 and Aethalometer prototype with extended wavelength range (Inter-AE)	WCCAP, DE (CL)	Complete
21	C1-CiGAS-CH-4	Università degli studi di Urbino- Italy	Calibration of NM-VOCs - CaliVOC	CiGAS-CH, CH (CL)	Cancelled
22	C1-ATMOS-1	University of Modena and Reggio Emilia	BBAC TO Athens (Black-Brown carbon Aerosol Campaign ThroughOut Athens)	ATMOS, GR (OBS)	Complete
23	C1-HELIOS-1	Research Center for Eco-Environmental Sciences (RCEES), Chinese Academy of Science (Beijing)	SURveying the Reactivity of Carbonyl Oxides using Symmetrical Alkenes (SURCOSA)	HELIOS, FR (ASC)	Complete
24	C1-USRL-4	Estonian University of Life Sciences	Sampling system for atmospheric volatile organic compounds measurements using unmanned aerial vehicles in different altitudes - ASVOCUAV	USRL, CY (MOB)	Complete
25	C1-EVASO-2	National Research Council of Italy	Integration of near-surface and vertical NO2 observations (INESV-NO2)	EVASO, PT (OBS)	Complete
26	C1-ISOLAB/CESAR-7	Institute for Nuclear Research	Hungarian Urban Greenhouse Gas Observations (HUGO)	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
27	C1-MAC-1	ETH Zürich	Concentration and chemical composition contribution of Ice Nucleating particles from Biomass Burning emissions (IN-BB)	MAC, UK (ASC)	Complete

28	C1-EVASO-1	Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial	Lidar data In a RT model for dust direct radiative effect estimation and evaluation against solar measurements (LiRTaSoM)	EVASO, PT (OBS)	Complete
29	C1-USRL-1	University of Reading	Diurnal vAriation of the vertically resolved siZe distribution in the Saharan Air Layer (DAZSAL)	USRL, CY (MOB)	Complete
30	C1-AIDA-2	Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)	Dust-induced ice nucleation: Effects of MIneralological COmposition and Size (MICOS)	AIDA, DE (ASC)	Complete
31	C1-KASCs-1	North-West University	Boreal and savanna fire aerosol ageing (BASFAA)	KASCs, FI (ASC)	Complete
32	C1-USRL-3	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Aerosol vertical profiling with lidars and drones (EVIAN)	USRL, CY (MOB)	Complete
33	ATMO-TNA-1-33	University of Evora	Ground-based/Satellite Synergies for TrAcers Monitoring in Urban Areas. (GSS-TAMUA)	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
34	C1-ISOLAB/CESAR-2	NILU-Norwegian Institute for Air Research	High latitude measurements of deuterium in methane from the Zeppelin Observatory-HALO	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
35	C1-CAO-1	Karsa Oy	Thermo Desorption – Multischeme chemical IONization inlet – Mass Spectrometer (TD-MION-MS) for atmospheric aerosol precursor and security research – proof of concept	CAO, CY (OBS)	Complete
36	C1-EUPHORE/SMEAR II-1	Aerosol d.o.o.	Advanced carbonaceous aerosol apportionment using Total Carbon Analyzer and newly developed Aethalometer prototype with extended wavelength range (ACAA:TC-BC 9λ)	SMEAR II, FI (OBS), EUPHORE, ES (ASC)	Complete

37	C1-RADO-3	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	Training of hands-on operation of Lidars and data analysis at RODA.	RADO, RO (OBS)	Complete
38	C1- KASCs -2	The Chinese University of Hong Kong	Probing Reactivity and Hygroscopicity Changes of Methanesulfonic Acid against OH Heterogeneous Oxidation using a Smog Chamber (MSAOH_CHAM)	KASCs, FI (ASC)	Complete
39	C1-RADO-2	Czech Hydrometeorological Institute (CHMI) / Institute of Chemical Process Fundamentals of the Czech Academy of Sciences (CAS)	SCC setup, testing and data check for the CHMI lidar	RADO, RO (OBS)	Complete
40	C1-ISOLAB/CESAR-1	INSTAAR, University of Colorado Boulder	BUDDS - Boulder-Utrecht Delta Deuterium Samples	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
41	C1-CESAM-1	Tel-Aviv University	Dust in the Polluted EnVironment and its CLimatic Effects (DEViLE)	CESAM, FR (ASC)	Cancelled
42	C1- CMN-PV/OPAR -1	Stockholm University	Net interactions between aerosol populations, fog and clouds under natural and anthropogenic influences (NetAeFoCs)	CMN-PV, IT (OBS) , OPAR, FR (OBS)	Complete
43	C1-CESAM-3	University of Gothenburg	Characterization and Quantification of "Water-On" Surface Catalysis in the context of Atmospheric Science (WOCATS)	CESAM, FR (ASC)	Complete

44	C1-AGORA4	Instituto Federal de São Paulo	Characterizing the role of thermal inversions and ABL dynamics on pollen concentration at surface: synergy between microwave radiometer, Doppler and Aerobiological techniques. (CEVADA)	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
45	C1-ISOLAB/CESAR-8	Institute of Environmental Physics, Heidelberg University	CH ₄ source identification with $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -CH ₄ and δD -CH ₄ on the regional scale	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
46	C1-FKL-1	University of Birmingham	Impact of shipping emissions on particulate matter pollution over the Eastern Mediterranean Sea (ISE-PM)	FKL, GR (OBS)	Complete
47	C1-FMCOMLab1	The Cyprus Institute	STANDARDIZED MOBILE PLATFORMS (STAMOS)	FCoMLab, FI (MOB)	Cancelled
48	C1-USRL-2	University of Ioannina	MACROSCOPIC	USRL, CY (MOB)	Cancelled
49	C1-SBO-2	Technische Universität Braunschweig	High-Frequency Spectral Induced Polarization Monitoring of Atmosphere-Cryosphere-Interactions (FROZEN)	SBO, AT (OBS)	Complete
50	C1-IASC-1	Aix Marseille University	PROXI : atmospheric fate and impact of Piperitone: Reactivity, Oxidation products and SOA formation	IASC, IE (ASC)	Complete
51	C1-WOS-1	University of Granada	ICARUS: Implementation of Combined lidar techniques for the retrieval of Aerosol fluxes in Rural and Urban Sites.	WOS, PL (OBS)	Complete
52	C1-CiGAS-CH-2	University of Eastern Finland	Unraveling controls on N ₂ O emissions from permafrost soils by using isotope analysis	CiGAS-CH, CH (CL)	Complete

53	C1-LACROS-2	Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial (INTA)	Lidar-radar synergy studies with advanced experience in other instrumentation (Raman lidar and cloud radar) (LIRASYS)	LACROS, DE (MOB)	Complete
54	C1-SIRTA-1	University of Nova Gorica	The Influence of the Mixing State on Aerosol Light Absorption (IMSALA)	SIRTA, FR (OBS)	Complete
55	C1-FORTH-MS-C-1	National Research Council of Italy (CNR)	Direct determination of secondary aerosol formation in the Po Valley through mobile reaction chamber technologies	FORTH-MS-C, GR (MOB)	Complete
56	C1-CiGAS-CH-3	Institute of Environmental Physics, Heidelberg University	N2O isotope analysis (calibration and sample comparison)	CiGAS-CH, CH (CL)	Cancelled
57	C1-CESAM-2	Tampere University	Volatile Particles from Sustainable Aviation Fuel (VP-SAF)	CESAM, FR (ASC)	Complete
58	C1-RADO-1	University of Warsaw	Towards development of FLUorescence-Mle-Raman mobile lidar (FLUMIRA)	AGORA, ES (OBS) , RADO, RO (OBS)	Complete
59	C1- CMN-PV -5	Universidade de Evora	Measurements Intercomparison for New Spectroscopic Instrument Calibration (MINSPEC)	CMN-PV, IT (OBS)	Complete
60	C1-FMI-PAL-SOD-2	IEK-7: Stratosphere, Forschungszentrum Jülich	Observations of Stratospheric TRace gases Influencing Climate using High-altitude platforms (OSTRICH)	FMI PAL-SOD, FI (OBS)	Complete
61	C1-AGORA5	The French Aerospace Lab (ONERA)	Lidar LOW-height profiling field campaign for ABL characterization (LILOW-ABL)	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
62	C1-SBO-1	Utrecht University	OMASC - Studying Organic Matter in Surface Snow, Cloudwater and Aerosol Filter Samples	SBO, AT (OBS)	Complete

63	C1-WOS-2	National Institute of Space Research	Structure and dynamics of the planetary boundary layer in urban environment ecosystem. (BOLAUR)	WOS, PL (OBS)	Complete
64	C1-CAO/USRL-1	University of Groningen	New Particle Formation in the MEDiterranean region - insights into precursor and cluster composition (NPF-MED)	CAO, CY (OBS), USRL, CY (MOB)	Complete
65	C1- CMN-PV -3	University of Bergen	Radio Interferometric Characterisation of High Energy Sources from Thunderstorms (RICHEST)	CMN-PV, IT (OBS)	Complete
66	C1- CMN-PV -4	Terra Modus Consultants Limited	Medusa Enhanced Volatile Organic Compounds (MEVOC)	CMN-PV, IT (OBS)	Complete
67	C1-ATMOS-2	Bolu Abant İzzet Baysal University (BAİBÜ)	Source Apportionment and Health Impact Assessment of Biomass Burning Organic Aerosols in Duzce (Turkey)	ATMOS, GR (OBS), FKL, GR (OBS)	Complete
68	C1- CMN-PV -2	Ecole Polytechnique Federale de Lausanne	Determination of Aerosol Acidity and Secondary Aerosol Formation in the Po Valley	CMN-PV, IT (OBS)	Complete
69	C1-AGORA-2	EAFIT University	Multichannel Raman Lidar measurements and PROCESSING CHAIN (MARPROCH)	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
70	2022-0000000012	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)	Giant airborne particle profiling (GRAIN)	USRL, CY (MOB)	Cancelled
71	2022-0000000023	Vaisala Oyj	CL61-4UrbanABL: testing the added-value of novel CL61 automatic ceilometer measurements for atmospheric boundary layer profiling in an urban environment.	SIRTA, FR (OBS)	Complete

72	2022-0000000024	Sunset Laboratory BV	Prototype field analyzer application for simultaneous real-time measurements of Organic Elemental, Black and Brown Carbon fractions using a dual-wavelength laser set-up. DUal Carbon Analyzer with Thermal Optical method (DUCATO)	BCN, ES (OBS)	Complete
73	2022-0000000027	Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (BIRA-IASB)	Ruisdael Rotterdam 2022 campaign	CESAR, NL (OBS)	Complete
74	2022-0000000031	University of Oulu	1st ECCINT CIS intercomparison for LWC: ECCINT-INT01	SBO, AT (OBS)	Complete
75	2022-0000000034	University of Helsinki	Reducing uncertainties in atmospheric dispersion and carbon emissions observations over Paris using LES modelling (LESParis)	SIRTA, FR (OBS)	Complete
76	2022-0000000052	National Institute of Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Investigating the Light Absorption properties of worldwide Dust aErosols (ILIADE)	CESAM, FR (ASC)	Complete
77	2022-0000000053	IMT Nord Europe	Ozone Chemistry of Two oxygEnated Terpenes (OCTET)	ESC-Q-UAIC, RO (ASC)	Complete
78	2022-0000000055	University of Hertfordshire	Arctic Multi-Phase cLoud Experiment (AMPLE)	FMI PAL-SOD, FI (OBS)	Complete
79	2022-0000000061	Stockholm University	Chlorine-initiated oxidation of biomass burning emissions	PACS-C2, CH (ASC)	Complete

80	2022-0000000064	Aerosol d.o.o.	Long-term and high-time-resolution validation of advanced total carbon-black carbon (TC-BC(λ)) method for apportionment of primary and secondary carbonaceous aerosols in the western Mediterranean basin (WMB: TC-BC(λ))	BCN, ES (OBS)	Complete
81	2022-0000000075	Palas GmbH	Cloud Droplet Analyzer (CDA)	SBO, AT (OBS)	Complete
82	2022-0000000084	University of Groningen	EMME-CARE autumn school - Analysis of aerosols, air pollution and their sources in the Eastern Mediterranean	CAO, CY (OBS)	Cancelled
83	2022-0000000086	Senseair	Evaluation of a new low-cost, small-size multi-channel NDIR sensing platform for GHG concentration measurement with sub-ppm resolution	ICOS-ATC, FR (CL)	Complete
84	2022-0000000087	Fudan University	Simulating secondary organic aerosol (SOA) formation of aromatics and their products over diurnal cycles	SAPHIR, DE (ASC)	Complete
85	2022-0000000089	Università degli Studi di Milano-Bicocca	EXperimental determination of the Atmospheric heating Rate due to light absorbing aerosol in remote high Altitude sites (EXARA).	JFJ, CH (OBS)	Complete
86	2022-0000000091	Wolfson Atmospheric Chemistry Laboratories, Department of Chemistry, University of York, UK	Understanding the atmospheric chemistry of biomass burning emissions	EUPHORE, ES (ASC)	Complete

87	2022-0000000092	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	Radon flux estimation by different direct methods in an agricultural field of the south of Paris (France) (RaFlux)	SIRTA, FR (OBS)	Complete
88	2022-0000000093	Centro de Ciências e Tecnologias Nucleares, Instituto Superior Técnico	Chemical source profiling of exhaust and non-exhaust traffic emission sources in Portugal (CSPENE)	ATMOS, GR (OBS)	Complete
89	2022-0000000094	Stockholm University	1st ECCINT CIS intercomparison for LWC: ECCINT-INT01	SBO, AT (OBS)	Complete
90	2022-0000000095	CIMEL	Characterization Of Aerosols In The subtropical nOrth atlaNtic (COALITION)	ISAF - IZO, ES (OBS)	Complete
91	2022-0000000098	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne	Vertical aerosol profiles during the Pallas Ice Cloud Experiment 2022 - VAP-PaCE	FMI PAL-SOD, FI (OBS)	Complete
92	2022-0000000103	Royal Holloway University of London	BorMIS - Boreal methane isotope studies	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
93	2022-0000000104	University of Bremen	Ruisdael Rotterdam 2022 campaign	CESAR, NL (OBS)	Complete
94	2022-0000000106	LSCE	Methane (CH ₄) Leaks: Drone-based In-situ Quantification (CH ₄ LKIDIQI)	USRL, CY (MOB)	Complete
95	2022-0000000109	Institute of Physical Chemistry Polish Academy of Sciences	The Secondary Organic Aerosol (SOA) Formation and Evolution in the Forest Atmosphere (ForestSOA)	ACD-C / LACIS-T, DE (ASC)	Complete
96	2022-0000000110	University of Warsaw, Faculty of Physics	Pollen Observations with Lidar - Laser Exploring in Non-invasive Atmospheric Techniques (POLLENAT)	BCN, ES (OBS)	Complete
97	2022-0000000111	Charles University	Analysis of the Stable isotope Composition of the Greenland Glacial Greenhouse Gases (ASC4G)	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
98	2022-0000000112	Laboratoire de Meteorologie Physique	1st ECCINT CIS intercomparison for LWC: ECCINT-INT01	SBO, AT (OBS)	Complete

99	2022-0000000113	University "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" Iasi	Atmospheric investigations of compounds emitted from BIOMass BUrning: FURfuryl alcohol and 3-NItroCatechol BIOBUFUNIC	QUAREC, DE (ASC)	Complete
100	2022-0000000114	Finnish Meteorological Institute	Pollen Observations with Lidar - Laser Exploring in Non-invasive Atmospheric Techniques (POLLENAT)	BCN, ES (OBS)	Complete
101	2022-0000000117	Finnish Meteorological Intitute	Chemical composition of PM1 in Helsinki by RI-Urban (HelRI-Urban)	ACMCC @SIRTA, FR (CL)	Complete
102	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000001	University of Hertfordshire	MPICCE	AIDA, DE (ASC)	Complete
103	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000002	LSCE	H2SSDIQ	USRL, CY (MOB)	Complete
104	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000005	University of Manchester	AE-DD	CESAM, FR (ASC)	Complete
105	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000011	The Cyprus Institute	SOP-CIMS	ACD-C / LACIS-T, DE (ASC)	Complete
106	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000013	Coventry University	IMPACT	ChAMBRé, IT (ASC)	Complete
107	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000016	CIMEL	EVOLUTION	ISAF - IZO, ES (OBS)	Complete
108	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000024	Max-Planck-Institute for Chemistry, Mainz, Germany	NORACHNO	SMEAR II, FI (OBS)	Complete
109	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000044	Utrecht University	ISAMO (Iron Salt Atmospheric Methane Oxidation in Sahara dust mixed with sea spray aerosol)	ISAF - IZO, ES (OBS)	Complete
110	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000047	Korea Polar Research Institute	HaloAA	CI GAS-CH, CH (CL)	Complete
111	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000049	TOFWERK AG	TEDIMS-ASC	QUAREC, DE (ASC)	Complete
112	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000051	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	TS@IZO	ISAF - IZO, ES (OBS)	Complete
113	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000052	JB Hyperspectral Devices GmbH	HAVAR-SIF	CESAR, NL (OBS)	Complete

114	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000053	Menapia Ltd.	MTV	CESAR, NL (OBS)	Complete
115	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000054	Stûv S.A. and University of Namur	GO40VOC	PACS-C2, CH (ASC)	Complete
116	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000056	Federal Institute of Metrology METAS	IntACoLSS	EUPHORE, ES (ASC)	Complete
117	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000058	University of Dundee	WoodToxMec	KASCs, FI (ASC)	Complete
118	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000059	GRASP SAS	CALVANeph	WCCAP, DE (CL)	Complete
119	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000063	University of Groningen	CS-CAINA	AIDA, DE (ASC)	Complete
120	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000064	University of Wuppertal	CEAST	IASC, IE (ASC)	Complete
121	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000071	Helmholtz-Zentrum hereon	PIRAthe	ATMOS, GR (OBS)	Complete
122	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000082	University of York	ADoNGS	ESC-Q-UAIC, RO (ASC)	Complete
123	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000086	National Research Council - Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate (CNR-ISAC)	ALADIN4AQ	SIRTA, FR (OBS)	Complete
124	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000091	Istanbul Technical University	ImPoWS	FKL, GR (OBS)	Complete
125	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000094	Global Change Research Institute, Czech Academy of Sciences	ToK-HigTal	JFJ, CH (OBS)	Complete
126	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000096	University of Évora	SAFEground	SIRTA, FR (OBS)	Complete
127	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000099	Purdue University	AIDA-SPMSI	AIDA, DE (ASC)	Complete
128	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000100	The Cyprus Institute	OXALEAST	ATMOS, GR (OBS)	Complete
129	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000105	Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD)	QCinSCC	CIAO, IT (OBS)	Complete
130	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000111	University of Bologna	NIADA	FKL, GR (OBS)	Complete

131	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000112	Bolu Abant Izzet Baysal University, Faculty of Engineering, Environmental Engineering Department	PARTICLE	ATMOS, GR (OBS) , FKL, GR (OBS)	Complete
132	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000114	Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research (TROPOS)	ADLER	USRL, CY (MOB)	Cancelled
133	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000115	University of Birmingham	RAC-PM	ATMOS, GR (OBS)	Complete
134	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000122	Origins.earth	UAS-GHG-T	USRL, CY (MOB)	Cancelled
135	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000123	Eurac Research	AQUINAS	ATMOS, GR (OBS)	Complete
136	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000124	University of Genoa	SENS4AIR	QUAREC, DE (ASC)	Complete
137	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000125	University of Freiburg	ABL-NET	SIRTA, FR (OBS)	Complete
138	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000127	Institute of Chemistry, Moldova	HYPER-ATMO	ESC-Q-UAIC, RO (ASC)	Complete
139	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000131	National Physical Laboratory, UK	IsoN2O	CiGAS-CH, CH (CL)	Complete
140	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000133	AGH University of Science and Technology, Faculty of Physics and Applied Computer Science, Krakow, Poland	e-BC	ATMOS, GR (OBS)	Complete
141	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000135	UNIVERSITY OF TIRANA	SAAA	CAO, CY (OBS)	Complete
142	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000138	National Centre for Scientific Research "Demokritos"	AERO-CHEM	CAO, CY (OBS)	Complete
143	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000142	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	BIOECOS	MAC, UK (ASC)	Complete

144	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000025	Environmental Engineering Dept., Democritus University of Thrace	DIONYSOS	AURA, DK (ASC)	Complete
145	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000030	University of Turin	ENVIFATE	ESC-Q-UAIC, RO (ASC)	Complete
146	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000032	Department of Physical Geography and Ecosystem Science, Lund University, Sweden	INAS	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
147	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000034	Peking University		SAPHIR, DE (ASC)	Complete
148	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000035	ETH Zurich	ORACLE	CESAM, FR (ASC)	Complete
149	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000037	University of Cambridge	LICEN	CESAM, FR (ASC)	Complete
150	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000039	Aix-Marseille Université	UP-VOC	BCN, ES (OBS)	Complete
151	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000041	AGH University of Krakow	ICCME	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
152	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000044	University of Reading	MuWMAS	SMEAR II, FI (OBS)	Cancelled
153	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000045	University of Nova Gorica	OOFSA	BCN, ES (OBS)	Complete
154	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000046	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	SBO_INP_23	SBO, AT (OBS)	Complete
155	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000048	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology - IMK/ASF	MIRVARESA	HELIOS, FR (ASC)	Complete
156	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000049	Leipzig University	EMPOS	SMEAR II, FI (OBS)	Complete
157	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000050	University of Leicester	N/A	SAPHIR, DE (ASC)	Complete
158	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000053	University of Granada	IBERIA	EVASO, PT (OBS)	Complete
159	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000054	University of Eastern Finland	MeJA-KOP	HELIOS, FR (ASC)	Complete
160	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000055	ETH Zürich, Switzerland	none	ChAMBRé, IT (ASC)	Complete
161	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000056	University "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" Iasi	FURANMEOL	QUAREC, DE (ASC)	Complete

162	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000057	The Climate and Environmental Research Institute NILU	HALO2	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
163	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000066	TU Wien	ESSENCE	SMEAR II, FI (OBS)	Complete
164	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000069	TU Wien	BISAF	FMI PAL-SOD, FI (OBS)	Complete
165	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000006	University of San Diego	CPoSm	CESAM, FR (ASC)	Complete
166	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000012	University of Copenhagen	ISAMO (Iron Salt Aerosol Methane Oxidation)	EUPHORE, ES (ASC)	Complete
167	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000021	UCA (Université Clermont Auvergne)	BactLight	ChAMBRé, IT (ASC)	Complete
168	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000022	University of Leipzig	BIO-HUM	ChAMBRé, IT (ASC)	Complete
169	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000030	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	BC-MAC	SMEAR II, FI (OBS)	Complete
170	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000034	University of Nottingham	Delhi-OX	SAPHIR, DE (ASC)	Complete
171	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000043	INAF-OACN (Italian National AstroPhysics institute - Observatory of Capodimonte)	MicroMED	ARN, ES (OBS)	Complete
172	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000045	Indian Institute of Technology Madras, Chennai	EI-UTO	FCoMLab, FI (MOB)	Complete
173	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000046	Stockholm University - ACES	Uplso	PACS-C2, CH (ASC)	Complete
174	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000047	University of Bern	H2O-IsoVHP	FMI PAL-SOD, FI (OBS)	Complete

175	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000048	Aarhus university	AOPACH	HTM, SE (OBS)	Complete
176	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000053	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	LAPCINDI-3	CESAR, NL (OBS)	Complete
177	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000054	Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México	CINDI-3	CESAR, NL (OBS)	Complete
178	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000065	Department of Environmental Chemistry and Air Research, Technische Universität Berlin	FeNTASI	ATMOS, GR (OBS), MHD, IE (OBS)	Complete
179	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000068	Scarabelli Ghini	Ed-ATMO	FKL, GR (OBS)	Complete
180	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000071	Columbia University	NewAMS	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
181	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000075	University of Evora	SP@CIDI	CESAR, NL (OBS)	Complete
182	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000077	INTA (National Institute of Aerospace Technologies)	INTACINDI3	CESAR, NL (OBS)	Complete
183	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000080	CNR-ISAC	ITSKYIC	CESAR, NL (OBS)	Complete
184	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000083	School of Biological Sciences, University of Aberdeen	ATMO-SOC	CMN-PV, IT (OBS)	Complete
185	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000084	Paul Scherrer Institute	LUMINOUS	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
186	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000085	Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research (TROPOS)	CWCOMP-MFT	CO-PDD, FR (OBS)	Complete

187	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000091	National Research Council of Italy (CNT) - Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate (ISAC)	WAVE	EVASO, PT (OBS)	Complete
188	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000096	University of Suwon	CINDI-3	CESAR, NL (OBS)	Complete
189	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000098	Sunset Laboratory BV	DETONATE	ATMOS, GR (OBS), PANGEA, GR (OBS)	Complete
190	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000105	Purdue University	SPMS@JFJ	JFJ, CH (OBS)	Complete
191	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000106	University of Copenhagen	ClimSox	SAPHIR, DE (ASC)	Complete
192	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000107	Pukyong National University	CINDI-3	CESAR, NL (OBS), CCRES-NL @CESAR, NL (CL), ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
193	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000111	University of Eastern Finland	SAPHURBAN	SAPHIR, DE (ASC)	Complete
194	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000112	ENEA - Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development	MIND-BB	EUPHORE, ES (ASC)	Complete
195	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000117	Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial (INTA)	MAR-CCN	OPAR, FR (OBS)	Cancelled
196	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000118	CNRS, University of Lille, Laboratoire d'Optique Atmosphérique	MAMS-CINDI	CESAR, NL (OBS)	Complete

197	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000122	University of Birmingham	HL-Dust	CESAM, FR (ASC)	Complete
198	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000126	University of Michigan	VVISP	PACS-C2, CH (ASC)	Complete
199	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000129	Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial (INTA)	AEROHYGRO	NAOK, CZ (OBS)	Complete
200	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000130	Department of Environmental Chemistry and Air Research, Technische Universität Berlin	INFeRNO	PACS-C2, CH (ASC)	Complete
201	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000131	University of Szeged	MuWaPAS	AIDA, DE (ASC), CCice @AIDA, DE (CL)	Complete
202	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000133	Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS) - IRCELYON	OS-MS	PACS-C2, CH (ASC)	Complete
203	ATMO-TNA-5G--0000000135	Code Academy Berlin	TIDA-CIAO	CIAO, IT (OBS)	Complete
204	ATMO-TNA-6M--0000000031	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	Exploration of seasonal changes in soil characteristics using Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) to assess the occurrence of permafrost in high alpine terrain at Hoher Sonnblick, Austria.	SBO, AT (OBS)	Complete
205	ATMO-TNA-6M--0000000046	Deakin University	SEPPORA	PACS-C2, CH (ASC)	Complete
206	ATMO-TNA-6M--0000000049	Helmholtz Munich	IAPtox	MAC, UK (ASC)	Complete

207	ATMO-TNA-6M--0000000052	University of York	PHOTO-SOLV	ESC-Q-UAIC, RO (ASC)	Complete
208	ATMO-TNA-6M--0000000057	VITO	MEMU	WOS, PL (OBS)	Complete
209	ATMO-TNA-6M--0000000063	Italian National Research Council - Institute of Marine Sciences (CNR - ISMAR)	ALIO	WOS, PL (OBS), AMP, PL (MOB)	Complete
210	ATMO-TNA-6M--0000000064	Institut National de Recherche et Sécurité	POPSURF	IASC, IE (ASC)	Complete
211	ATMO-TNA-6M--0000000079	University of Hawaii	PeatCReu24	OPAR, FR (OBS)	Complete
212	ATMO-TNA-6M--0000000083	University of Manchester	POLFRAG	ChAMBRé, IT (ASC)	Complete
213	ATMO-TNA-6M--0000000002	Hacettepe University	Chemical Characterization of Background Aerosol Load of the Eastern Mediterranean	FKL, GR (OBS)	Complete
214	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000009	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich	In-situ observation of aerosol-cloud-interaction around 0 °C at Sonnblick Observatory	SBO, AT (OBS)	Complete
215	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000012	IMT Nord Europe	Oxygenated Terpenes: Temperature-Dependent Ozone Kinetics	ESC-Q-UAIC, RO (ASC)	Complete
216	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000013	Utrecht University	Continuous isotopic methane measurements at the mountain station Monte Cimone (northern Italy).	CMN-PV, IT (OBS)	Complete
217	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000016	Max-Planck-Institut for Chemistry	Biosphere-Atmosphere Interactions and the Reactive Nitrogen Budget: Vertical Profiles of Key Species	SMEAR II, FI (OBS)	Complete
218	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000018	ULiege	Advanced Sensor Systems for NH ₃ Emission	SIRTA, FR (OBS)	Complete

219	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000019	National Technical University of Athens	AGORA International Doctoral Summer School: training school on characterization of atmospheric aerosol using in-situ and remote sensing techniques (2nd edition).	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
220	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000024	CITEDEF (Centro de Investigaciones Cientificas y Tecnicas del Ministerio de Defensa)	Lidar Analysis TOols and methodS	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
221	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000025	UCA (Université Clermont Auvergne)	Evolution of the bacterial transcriptome following exposure to nitrous oxides	ChAMBRé, IT (ASC)	Complete
222	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000026	University of Manchester	Improved Scientific Knowledge of Clouds, Ice CrYstals and Aerosols through LABoratory Access of a New Dynamic Cloud Chamber	AIDA, DE (ASC)	Complete
223	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000027	CNRS/University of Lille	Analysis of joined Remote Sensing and In-situ observations for Mediterranean aerosol analysis	CAO, CY (OBS)	Complete
224	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000033	Institute of Chemical Process Fundamentals CAS (ICPF)	Investigation of aerosol hygroscopicity - comparison of dual nephelometry and HTDMA system at marine background station in Spain	ARN, ES (OBS)	Complete
225	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000034	Coventry University	Investigation of the aerosolisation dynamics and biological interactions of GenX "forever chemicals"	ChAMBRé, IT (ASC)	Complete
226	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000036	University of Wroclaw	Pollen and Fine Particulate Monitoring, Forecasting, and Analysis	RADO, RO (OBS)	Complete

227	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000040	Istanbul University-Cerrahpasa	Fine and ultrafine Aerosols from Megacity of Istanbul: Sources and their possible impact on health	ATMOS, GR (OBS)	Complete
228	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000041	International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development	AGORA International Doctoral Summer School: Advancing Atmospheric Aerosol Characterization through In-Situ and Remote Sensing Techniques.	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Cancelled
229	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000049	University of Warsaw, Faculty of Physics	Integrating Pollen in-situ measurements with Lidar for ENhanced detection	OPAR, FR (OBS)	Complete
230	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000054	CNRS (Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique)	MC3: Molecular Composition of Clouds at mt. Cimone	CMN-PV, IT (OBS)	Complete
231	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000056	University of Warsaw - Faculty of Physics	Industrial POLLution Sensing with synergic techniques.	CESAR, NL (OBS), RADO, RO (OBS), ICOS-ATC, FR (CL)	Complete
232	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000058	National Institute of Research and Development for Optoelectronics- INOE	In situ and remote sensing assessment of bio-aerosols	WOPAS, PL (OBS), WOS, PL (OBS) , AMP, PL (MOB)	Complete
233	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000059	Bolu Abant İzzet Baysal University, Environmental Engineering Department	Factors Regulating the Emissions and Sources of New Particle Formation at SMEAR II Station in Summer and Winter	SMEAR II, FI (OBS)	Complete
234	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000064	Indiana University	Elucidating Hidden Renoxification Mechanisms from Nitrate Photolysis in Organic Aerosol Particles	ACD-C / LACIS-T, DE (ASC)	Complete
235	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000065	Indiana University	Nitrogen Oxide Emissions from Iron-Catalyzed Reactions of Organic Nitrate Esters in Aerosols	ACD-C / LACIS-T, DE (ASC)	Complete

236	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000070	British Antarctic Survey	Isotopic signature of methane on Atlantic transects measured onboard RRS Sir David Attenborough.	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
237	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000073	University of Warsaw	ZeFir Training Workshop	SIRTA, FR (OBS)	Complete
238	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000075	Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate (CNR-ISAC)	Ice nucleating particles Detection	AIDA, DE (ASC)	Complete
239	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000076	Cyprus Institute	Performance Evaluation of a Novel Aerosol Mass Spectrometer	FORTH-MS, GR (MOB)	Complete
240	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000078	Tofwerk AG	Resolving the formation and fate of atmospheric organic peroxy radicals	QUAREC, DE (ASC)	Complete
241	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000079	University College Cork	Hands-on Training on ASC	QUAREC, DE (ASC)	Complete
242	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000082	Turkish Ministry of Environment, Urbanisation and Climate Change	Capacity Building for the Development of Analysis of Emission and Mitigation Options of Greenhouse Gases in Türkiye	ATMOS, GR (OBS), FKL, GR (OBS)	Cancelled
243	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000085	Institute of Physics Belgrade	Improvement of Lidar Operation and data Analysis in Belgrade	RADO, RO (OBS)	Complete
244	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000088	Max Planck Institute for Dynamics and Self-Organization	In-situ Measurement of Particles, Aerosols, Clouds and Turbulence (IMPACT)	FMI PAL-SOD, FI (OBS)	Complete
245	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000092	University of Cambridge, TU Delft	Atmospheric composition measurements at Larnaca International Airport in Cyprus	CAO, CY (OBS), USRL,CY (MOB)	Cancelled
246	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000101	Clean Air Task Force	Portable Equipment Calibration for Improved Sensing Efficiency	ATMOS, GR (OBS)	Complete
247	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000102	Max Planck Institute for Chemistry	The Role Of Monoterpene Enantiomers in Aerosol Formation	CAO, CY (OBS)	Complete

248	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000105	Centre Nationale Recherches Scientifiques	Real-time monitoring of ultrafine and Secondary Particles In Urban Environments	FCoMLab, FI (MOB) - ATMO LAB	Complete
249	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000106	University "Alexandru Ioan Cuza"	Night-time Chemistry of trans- β -Farnesene	IASC, IE (ASC)	Complete
250	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000107	CNR-ISAC	ZeFir output analysis for evaluating mineral DUST transport events at Monte Cimone, Italy	SIRTA, FR (OBS)	Complete
251	ATMO-TNA-7--0000000110	Stockholm University	Isotopic source apportionment of carbon monoxide in South Asia and Indian Ocean Regions	ISOLAB-UU @CESAR, NL (CL)	Complete
252	ATMO-TNA-6M--0000000033	University of Warsaw	Oxidation of odorants depending on the time of day as a parameter in prediction the odorous range of municipal management facilities	HELIOS, FR (ASC)	Complete
253	ATMO-TNA-6M--0000000082	University of L'Aquila	Advancing ABL profiling synergy	SIRTA, FR (OBS)	Complete
254	ATMO-TNA-6M--0000000084	Technical University of Denmark (DTU)	Connect Tall Tower GHG Concentration Measurements	HTM, SE (OBS)	Complete
255	ATMO-TNA-3--0000000009	Len	EvalDBAP	WCCAP, DE (CL)	Complete
256	ATMO-TNA-4--0000000061	AeroSpec	MAC-IRS	ATMOS, GR (OBS)	Complete
257	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000021	Licel GmbH	APD Ground Loop Prevention	WOS, PL (OBS)	Complete
258	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000026	Aerosol d.o.o.	Intercomparison of optical absorption measurements using newly developed Aethalometer AE36 and AE36s with extended wavelength range (9-wavelengths)	WCCAP, DE (CL)	Complete
259	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000032	Aerosol d.o.o.	ACASXX-36s	ATMOS, GR (OBS)	Complete

260	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000040	Eventech	Eventech Time-Tagger Testing for Lidar Applications.	WOS, PL (OBS)	Complete
261	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000049	GRASP SAS		WOS, PL (OBS), AMP, PL (MOB)	Complete
262	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000054	Droplet Measurement Technologies, LLC	Cloud Aerosol Bioaerosol and Dust Interactions Experiment	CO-PDD, FR (OBS)	Complete
263	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000069	Picarro Inc		CO-PDD, FR (OBS)	Complete
264	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000070	RAYMETRICS SA		AMP, PL (MOB)	Complete
265	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000075	Raymetrics	PM Eye	USRL,CY (MOB)	Complete
266	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000077	European Sensor Systems S.A.		RADO, RO (OBS)	Complete
267	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000082	Raymetrics	MARSaccess	RADO, RO (OBS)	Complete
268	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000083	TENUM		ISAF - (IZO), ES (OBS)	Complete
269	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000084	Luper Technologies B.V.		IASC, IE (ASC)	Complete
270	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000094	Menapia Ltd.		CESAR, NL (OBS)	Complete
271	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000095	Menapia Ltd.		FMI PAL-SOD, FI (OBS)	Complete
272	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000097	GRASP Earth		WCCAP, DE (CL)	Complete
273	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000118	Dekati Ltd.		MAC, UK (ASC)	Complete
274	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000130	Aerospec SA	PARIS	SIRTA. FR (OBS)	Complete
275	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000132	IONICON Analytik GmbH		SIRTA. FR (OBS)	Cancelled
276	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000143	BJE Environmental Optics	CLEARQ	WOS, PL (OBS)	Complete
277	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000147	Aerosol d.o.o.		SIRTA, FR (OBS)	Complete
278	ATMO-TNA-6--0000000149	Observator Instruments		WOPAS, PL (OBS)	Complete
279	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000094	University of Évora	AUTUMN SCHOOL SENSORS & DRONES	The Cyprus Institute [CAO (OBS) - USRL (MOB)]	Complete

280	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000100	University of Oslo	AUTUMN SCHOOL SENSORS & DRONES	The Cyprus Institute [CAO (OBS) - USRL (MOB)]	Complete
281	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000113	Doctoral School at University of Silesia	AUTUMN SCHOOL SENSORS & DRONES	Empa [CiGAS-CH (CL)]	Complete
282	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000116	University of Warsaw	AUTUMN SCHOOL SENSORS & DRONES	Empa [CiGAS-CH (CL)]	Cancelled
283	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000121	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	AUTUMN SCHOOL SENSORS & DRONES	The Cyprus Institute [CAO (OBS) - USRL (MOB)]	Complete
284	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000122	University of Silesia in Katowice	AUTUMN SCHOOL SENSORS & DRONES	The Cyprus Institute [CAO (OBS) - USRL (MOB)]	Cancelled
285	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000135	Nuclear and Energy Research Institute - University of Sao Paulo	AUTUMN SCHOOL SENSORS & DRONES	Empa [CiGAS-CH (CL)]	Complete
286	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000138	Météo-France/Centre Nationale de Recherches Météorologiques	AUTUMN SCHOOL SENSORS & DRONES	The Cyprus Institute [CAO (OBS) - USRL (MOB)]	Complete
287	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000140	African Research Centre on Air Quality and Climate, University Mohammad VI Polytechnic, Benguerir, Morocco	AUTUMN SCHOOL SENSORS & DRONES	Empa [CiGAS-CH (CL)]	Complete
288	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000147	Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany	AUTUMN SCHOOL SENSORS & DRONES	Empa [CiGAS-CH (CL)]	Complete
289	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000149	Yildiz Technical University	AUTUMN SCHOOL SENSORS & DRONES	Empa [CiGAS-CH (CL)]	Complete
290	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000150	Yildiz Technical University	AUTUMN SCHOOL SENSORS & DRONES	Empa [CiGAS-CH (CL)]	Complete
291	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000154	University of Helsinki	AUTUMN SCHOOL SENSORS & DRONES	The Cyprus Institute [CAO (OBS) - USRL (MOB)]	Complete

292	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000006	Instituto Federal de São Paulo	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
293	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000018	University of Nova Gorica	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
294	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000021	Paul Scherrer Institut	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
295	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000024	Università degli Studi dell'Aquila	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
296	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000027	University of Genoa	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
297	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000032	Aarhus Univeristy	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
298	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000040	Gebze Technical University, Institute of Earth and Marine Sciences	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
299	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000065	National Meteorological Service of Argentina	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
300	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000066	National Institute of Meteorology and Hydrology of Bulgaria	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
301	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000067	University of Warsaw	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
302	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000073	CITEDEF (Centro de Investigaciones Cientificas y Tecnicas del Ministerio de Defensa)	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
303	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000075	University of Warsaw	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
304	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000080	Centro de Investigaciones en Láseres y Aplicaciones (CEILAP), CITEDEF	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
305	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000086	EPFL/Swiss Federal Institute of Metrology	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete

306	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000088	University of Maryland Baltimore County	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
307	ATMO-TNA-5--0000000089	Eafit university	AGORA SCHOOL	AGORA, ES (OBS)	Complete
308	FT-1	NASA	FT1-MLO_NASA-ISAF	ISAF - (IZO), ES (OBS)	Complete
309	FT-2	ECCC	FT2-MLO/ECCC-ISAF	ISAF - (IZO), ES (OBS)	Complete
310	FT-3	NOAA	FT3-MLO/NOAA-ISAF	ISAF - (IZO), ES (OBS)	Complete
311	Cal/Val 1	ESA	ESA	Multiple facilities	Complete
312	Cal/Val 2	EUMETSAT	EUMETSAT - Aerosol	Multiple facilities	Complete
313	Cal/Val 3	EUMETSAT	EUMETSAT - Clouds	Multiple facilities	Complete

